

Spline fitting tool for scientometric applications: estimation of citation peaks and publication time-lags

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Introduction

Bibliometric data are often hard to describe using theoretical models. Non-parametric regressions represent a powerful alternative to extract the system's constants. This paper presents a method for the implementation of such a tool using natural cubic splines (NCS) and their application in scientometrics.

Method

Using NCS to fit and interpolate bibliometric data, information such as the citation peak of journals and/or papers can be extracted. This approach gives a small interpolation error with low order polynomials thereby avoiding Runge's phenomenon.

To build a cubic spline on $n + 1$ data points, n cubic polynomials P_i are required. Their four coefficients are determined using interpolation and continuity conditions. This leaves $4n$ unknowns to be calculated using $4n-2$ equations. To obtain an NCS, two additional equations are introduced (Green & Silverman, 1994). This system is solved using linear transformations.

With a dense set of data, it is not optimal to have a perfect fit as data fluctuations might have an impact on the shape of the fitting curve. These fluctuations can be damped using a linear smoothing which associates each data point with its "damped image", creating a damped dataset \hat{g} . This smoothing results from a compromise between the residual sum of squares and the roughness of the function using the penalized sum of squares:

$$Pss(g) = \sum_{i=1}^n \{Y_i - g(x)\}^2 + \alpha \int_a^b (g''(t))^2 dt$$

Given a smoothing parameter α , the damped dataset \hat{g} is determined by minimising Pss over g :

$$\hat{g} = (I + \alpha K)^{-1} Y$$

Where I is the identity matrix and K is a n -by- n matrix obtained from the dataset and its second derivatives at each point.

Application

Using NCS, the citation peak of three journals was estimated (Figure 1A). The red lines represent the fitting obtained with the NCS ($\alpha = 0.5$). Unlike the traditional method, which takes the highest data point as the maximum, we extract it from the general shape of the curve. If one removes the highest data point for the journal *Blood*, the peak with the former method is shifted from 3 to 4 years whereas it remains the same (i.e., 3.4 years) using NCS. Thus, the method is robust against missing information and fluctuations which are frequent with small journals. Figure 1B summarizes the results of this application to citation peak calculation for 12,130 journals. Based on this figure, using a fixed 2-year citation window as is common usage clearly introduces a bias.

Figure 1. Number of citations per year for three journals

Identifying papers published with a given grant is an important challenge for research evaluation (Campbell *et al.*, 2010). One can use a publication window which includes the peak in the number of papers associated to a grant; this maximises the recall of supported papers while minimizing false positives. Based on experimental data, the publication peak for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in Canada was estimated to occur 2.75 years following the first year of funding using NCS. Yet, variations in the peak among subfields can have profound impact on the conclusions of evaluations. These variations will be analysed for the SSH and the health sciences.

References

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